

THE ISSUE OF INTERRELATION OF LANGUAGE AND POLITICS

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Abstract: This article defines the role of political terms in linguistics. The issue of the relationship between language and politics in the political process of society has been discussed. The importance of correct use of linguistic units is shown in the implementation of policy.

Keywords: political science, political term, language policy, linguistic factors, extralinguistic factors, policy instrument.

Each language is an open mirror reflecting the material and spiritual world, the integrity and existence of the speaker of this language, and is closely connected with the work and social activities of a person. Language itself is defined by a culture. We cannot be competent in the language if we do not also understand the culture that has shaped and informed it [1]. Therefore, any event or change that occurs in society is first of all reflected in the language. In the course of historical and socio-economic development, the vocabulary of the language is consistently developed and enriched. This wealth arises from the emergence of new words and terms expressing new concepts that have arisen as a result of the development of society. The vocabulary of our language, its lexical-semantic system, is constantly changing, while words denoting concepts or names of objects that are rarely used by members of society fall out of use as archaic words, and their place is taken by new words [7]. However, the number of words that fall out of use will be significantly less than the number of newly coined words. But in some cases, it may be the other way around. Of course, the withdrawal of lexical units from use occurs on the basis of linguistic and extralinguistic factors, the nature of language and the laws of language development. In this case, two main phenomena are observed:

1. With the disappearance of phenomena in society and nature, the words denoting them also fall out of use, leave the vocabulary of the modern language and become historical words.

2. In the process of language development, lexical units that cannot accurately, fully and precisely convey the meaning of an event, phenomenon or object fall out of use, and their place is taken by lexical units that accurately, fully and precisely convey their meaning [5].

The constant enrichment of vocabulary, as a social phenomenon, is one of the most fundamental laws of language development. Lexical development manifests itself in different ways and at different levels in different periods of society's development. New words are not invented, but rather existing word-formation affixes in the language, that is, the internal capabilities of a particular language and borrowings from another language. Invented words constitute a very small number in different languages. Russian linguist E.A. Zemskeya writes: "Let's think for a minute, let's say a new word is created without any connection to the old word. Then mastering the language would become extremely difficult, or impossible. The way to enrich the vocabulary is to further simplify its use and, most importantly, to describe the interconnected events and phenomena of real life through the existing interconnected words in the language. Thus, the relationship between words in language reflects the relationship between real objects and real events" [6].

The vocabulary of the language is constantly enriched with new words, as a result of which the language also develops. The main part of new words are terms. The development of science and technology gives rise to new terms and lays the foundation for technical progress. The reason is that science or industry cannot develop properly without scientific terminological support. Any change in society is first reflected in the language. At certain periods in the development of society, there are cases when the terminology of a particular area goes beyond certain narrow boundaries and is widely used in the common language. In particular, over the years of Uzbekistan's independence, many terms related to socio-political terminology have penetrated into the unlimited layer of literary language and are widely used in everyday speech. Terms such as "addressee," "bankrupt," "stock exchange," "dollar," "guest worker," "inventory," are actively used in our language as a product of independence [3].

As you know, words in every language have several meanings. The specific meaning of polysemantic words is determined by the context and structure of the sentence. Such words play an important role in making speech expressive, lively, concise and beautiful. At the same time, there are words that express one concept, limited to the scope of each language and having, basically, one meaning. Such words are found in various fields such as science, technology, art, politics, language and literature, crafts. In these areas, all attention is paid to the text alone. Therefore, the scientific, technical and political spheres require very clear speech.

As mentioned above, in order to be understandable to everyone, in linguistics, words related to the sphere of politics must be clearly defined, since politics, by its nature, has content that is constantly updated and reflects the latest news in the development of society and the state. Therefore, it is difficult to form a single universal model of political terms. Political science, within the framework of its subject, seeks to scientifically substantiate changes in the political life of society. This demonstrates the importance of studying political terms, which are an integral part of political science.

K.M. Musaev compares terminology as the vocabulary of a language with one city. In his opinion: "Although the terminology is built on the basis of a single plan, it does not appear suddenly. It is formed on the basis of historical conditions; different architects, designers, and inventors of different generations participate in its creation. They build each construction project after carefully studying it. This is what determines the specific complexity in regulating terminology [4].

Language plays an active role in the world of politics, and this role is constantly evolving. Political terms are a necessary tool of politics and power; they not only reflect reality, but also shape it through information influence. It ensures the transmission of political information, the formation of socio-political ideals, norms and values, and political convictions of citizens. Politics, in turn, serves as an effective factor in the development of language and linguistic relations.

Language is not only a means of communication, but also an instrument of control that determines the political behavior of citizens. In turn, the policy pursued by our state in the area of language planning and development has a great influence on its development and functioning. Therefore, we can talk about two aspects of the interaction between language and politics: 1) language as an instrument of politics 2) language as an object of politics. "In the first case, we are talking about the implementation of policy through language: here language is used as a means of influencing society to achieve certain political goals. Thus, language is a determining factor of political behavior and an instrument of political control.

It can be said that political knowledge occupies a special place in the development of society, and on this basis, it is possible to properly organize state and social construction and management. Today, the widespread development of political knowledge is shaping new views on political processes and political institutions. As a result, there is a need to modernize public administration and carry out large-scale reforms.

As is known, from the first days of independence, Uzbekistan embarked on the path of building a sovereign democratic state. The process of modernization in Uzbekistan continues today. On February 7, 2017, at the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the “Action Strategy” was announced, consisting of five priority areas aimed at the further development of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. These priority areas directly cover issues related to reforming state and public administration, developing the judicial and legal system, liberalizing the economy, strengthening activities in the social sphere, security and the effective implementation of foreign policy .

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated September 11, 2023 on the Strategy “Uzbekistan-2030” was published, which defines nine main areas of radical reform of the public administration system. This is also of great importance for the development of political knowledge in our country.

If we consider two ways in which language and politics interact, we can conclude that language and politics are closely interrelated. Specially selected linguistic units perform the function of linguistic influence, facilitating the implementation of political goals and relations. Politics, in turn, determines the direction of language development, its place and status in the country. Language is thus an integral part of the relationship between politics and power. However, we must not forget that state policy, like the state itself, depends largely on the language that shapes thinking and the cultural gene pool that unites the population into a single nation .

To sum up, it can be said that new political concepts and theories are being put forward every day in scientific centers of the world, and political science is being enriched with topics covering contemporary issues. Therefore, raising work in this area to a new level is one of the priority tasks in our country. This once again proves the need to study the stages of development, assimilation and application of political terms in everyday life.

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